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Elimination of Cassava Mosaic Disease Virus by Thermotherapy and Meristem Culture in Côte D'ivoire

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Abbreviations

MS-Murashige and Skoog

DNA-Deoxyribonucleic Acid

PCR-Polymerase Chain Reaction

TAS-ELISA- Triple Antibody Sandwich Enzyme-Linked Immuno Sorbent Assay

ACMV-African Cassava Mosaic Virus

BAP-6-Benzyle Amino-Purine

NAA-Naphthalene Acetic Acid

CTAB-Cetyltrimethylammonium Bromide

MS-Murashige and Skoog

2.4-D-Dichlorophenoxyacetic acid

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Abstract

Grown in Côte d'Ivoire by smallholders, cassava takes great part of food security and poverty decreasing. Cassava is most important crops in climate change context. Cultivation is done with cuttings derived from local varieties. Unfortunately, these cuttings are susceptible to cassava mosaic disease which is transfer from one crop to another one. Infected cassava plants produce low yields and tubers are bad quality. The aim of this paper is to evaluate performance of thermotherapy engineering associated with meristem culture for cassava cuttings sanitation. Ten cultivars of cassava were used. Fifteen cuttings of each cultivar were collected and subjected to a temperature varying from 32 to 39°C under a photoperiod of 16/8h and evaluated after three weeks. Thermotherapy associated with meristem culture was used to treat variety Yacé. The results obtained showed that thermotherapy allowed a cleaning of cassava cuttings at percentages ranging from 6 to 33%. In addition, thermotherapy and meristem culture of cultivar Yacé allowed to obtain a percentage of sanitation of 92 %.

Keywords : Cassava - Côte d'Ivoire - Meristem culture - Sanitation - Thermotherapy

INTRODUCTION

Once used as a subsistence crop during times of hunger, cassava has become a cash crop today (Thresh, 2006). This change is the result of high demand for derived products from cassava tubers such as attiéké (fermented cassava semolina), for local consumption and sub saharan export (N'zué B, 2007). Cassava plant adapts well to the effects of climate change and can grow on different soil types. Indeed, cassava is resistant to periods of prolonged drought and produces average yields on marginal soils (FAO, 2013). Despite the agronomic and economic benefits of cassava for food security and poverty reduction, the cassava during its development faces to major constraints such as viral diseases. In Côte d'Ivoire, cassava mosaic disease is caused by two major viruses, African Cassava Mosaic Virus (ACMV) and East African Cassava Mosaic

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Virus (EACMV) (Toualy *et al*, 2014). These are geminiviruses of the family Geminiviridae (Ogwok *et al*, 2015). Cassava mosaic disease is a systemic disease and is propagated by whitefly (*Bemisia tabaci*) by a semi-persistent method (Jeremiah, 2015). After cassava plant infection, the using of infected cuttings as planting materials becomes the second mode of disease spread (Munga *et al*, 2002). The use of cuttings prone to infection promotes transmission of mosaic disease from one cassava field to another and from one crop cycle to another over long distances (Legg JP *et al*, 2013). This results in a decrease in production ranging from 20 to 90 % (IITA, 2000). This pandemic therefore becomes a real threat to food security in Africa if it is not contained (Segnou *et al*, 2002). Various means of struggle exist. Those are : use of resistant varieties, or virus-free cuttings, as well as sanitation of the plot limit the occurrence of diseases in newly established plantations (Hillocks *et al*, 2003). Also, the systematic elimination of cassava shoots showing symptoms of juvenile stage virosis greatly reduces the spread of the disease (Legg *et al*, 2011). However, producers are reluctant to adopt improved varieties for reasons of late maturity and inadequate organoleptic properties (Mwamachi *et al*, 2005). To address this, plant biotechnology techniques such as thermotherapy and meristem culture are used as alternative ways to clean up local varieties of cassava (Zapata *et al*, 1995). Meristematic areas of infected plants are generally virus-free because they have not differentiated cells or contain minimal viral load (Wasswa *et al*, 2010). These same authors report that heat hinders the replication of viruses. In Côte d'Ivoire, these techniques are not vulgarized or are little used for the remediation of local plant species. The objective of this study is to contribute to improving the quality of cassava planting material by using thermotherapy and meristem culture methods.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Plant samples

The plant material consisted of cuttings and leaves collected on ten local cultivars of cassava namely Nsakperne, Antenne, Six-month and Gnonrongouin (South-East), Zogloblé, Afery and Demoiselle (Center), Diarassouba (North), Glagban (West) and Yacé (South). These cassava cultivars were grown in experimental field at the University Nangui Abrogoua. The leaves of excised cuttings exhibited symptoms of cassava mosaic disease.

Experimental design

The incubator is a cubic shape box of 1 m of side. The upper and lower faces are covered with plywood and the other four (4) faces are covered with transparent plastic. Six incandescent bayonet bulbs (60-watt) were installed indoors to serve as a source of heat and light (Figure 1). The electrical cable connecting the six bulbs simultaneously was connected to the mains voltage via a timer. Inside the incubator, 2-liter jars contain autoclaved soil at 121 °C, at a pressure of 1 bar for 30 min.

Serological status of cuttings

The serological status of the different cultivars was verified with the young leaves of cultivars showing the symptoms of the cassava mosaic disease. The TAS-ELISA test has been used (Clark *et al*, 1977). The strains of ACMV (African Cassava Mosaic Virus) and EACMV (East African Cassava Mosaic Virus) were detected using antibodies AS 0421-0421/2 and AS-0421-0421/4, respectively.

Cuttings thermotherapy

Cuttings were excised on plants with positive response to TAS-ELISA tests against the ACMV or the EACMV. For each cultivar, five cuttings were used, and three replicates were performed. The cuttings were planted in 2-liter pots in five rows in the incubator. The experiment was carried out with a photoperiod of 16/8 hours, a temperatures of 40 °C and 36 °C and a relative humidity of 65 %. Watering was done regularly to keep the substrate moistened. After four weeks of incubation, the number of cuttings inducing shoot buds was counted, then young leaves were excised to perform the TAS-ELISA.

Thermotherapy associated with meristem culture

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The cultivar Yacé was used in this experiment. It is the most cultivated cultivar by producers in Côte d'Ivoire. Its tuber is used to prepare a dish called "Attiéké" very appreciated by most of the Ivorian population. However, this cultivar is highly susceptible to cassava mosaic disease. In addition, compared to other cultivars, the rate of recovery of healthy plants by the thermotherapy technique remains low in Yacé cultivar. In order to improve this low rate, the apical meristems were isolated on the cuttings subjected to the treatment of thermotherapy. A pre-disinfection was performed by washing segments with tap water, then disinfection was carried out under a laminar flow hood, by soaking in 70 % ethanol for 3 min, followed by immersion in a calcium hypochlorite solution (3 %) containing a drop of Tween 20 for a duration of 3 min. The segments were subsequently rinsed four times in sterile distilled water. Then, the apical meristematic domes were excised under a binocular microscope with scalpel blades n°11 and placed on culture media (Figure 2).

Effect of medium culture medium composition on plants regeneration from meristems

For this study, the basic medium used was Murashige and Skoog with MS vitamins supplemented with sucrose 3 % and myo-inositol 0.1 g/l (Murashige and Skoog, 1962). Different hormones were added individually to the basic medium. Depending on the nature and concentration of the growth regulators, four media have been formulated. The meristems were placed on the respective media. The composition of each medium is shown in Table 1.

Effect of medium culture composition on shoots rooting

After three weeks of culture, the shoots were counted and then transferred on rooting media. MS basal medium without growth regulator and MS basal medium supplemented with NAA (0.01 mg/l) and BAP (0.05 mg/l) were tested for root induction.

Frequencies of apical meristem regeneration

The frequency of shoot induction was evaluated according to the following formula:

$$\% \text{ of shoot induction} = \frac{\text{Number of explants inducing shoots}}{\text{Total number of explants in culture}} \times 100$$

Rooting frequencies of shoot buds

After four weeks of culture in rooting medium, the percentage of rooted seedlings was calculated according to the following formula:

$$\% \text{ of rooting} = \frac{\text{number of rooted plants}}{\text{Total number of shoot buds}} \times 100$$

Health status of seedlings regenerated from apical meristem

Indexing was performed from leaf DNA extracts obtained with 26 plants regenerated from from apical meristems. Positive samples were diagnosed by PCR, with JSP primers whose sequences are shown in Table 2. After six weeks of culture, leaves were excised from in vitro plantlets regenerated from apical meristem. The leaves were used for indexing by enzymatic amplification test of nucleic acid sequences (PCR).

Cetyltrimethylammonium Bromide DNA Extraction Protocol (CTAB)

The protocol used for the extraction of DNA samples is that of Doyle and Doyle modified and adapted to our plant material (Doyle and Doyle, 1987). 0.3 g fresh leaf of each sample was milled in 1500 µl of CTAB buffer, vortexed and the mixture is incubated at 60 °C in a water bath for 60 minutes with gentle stirring. After which, the ground samples of the different samples are centrifuged at 20000 rpm for 10 min. Then 700 µl of the supernatant are collected in eppendorf tube (2 ml) to which 700 µl of chloroform isobutyl alcohol (CIA) are added. The mixture is vortexed for 5 min and then centrifuged for 10 min at 20000 rpm for 10 min. Then, 400 µl of the supernatant was removed and poured into an eppendorf tube and 400 µl of isopropanol were added. The whole was vortexed for 5 min to precipitate DNA. The mixture obtained is incubated at -80°C. for 30 min and then centrifuged at 20000 rpm for a period of 10 min. The pellet containing the DNA is taken up in 500 µl of 70 % ethanol. The mixture is centrifuged and the ethanol is discarded and the eppendorf tubes containing the pellets of the DNA of each sample are left open air

overnight for dehydration. The DNA is diluted in 100 µl of distilled water. This fraction was used to evaluate the amount of DNA from each fresh leaf sample. The different reagents and their concentrations, for a DNA sample, are shown in Table 2. Five µl of DNA solution were diluted to 1/50th and 20 µl of reagents were added.

PCR program

The PCR program is constituted a first denaturation phase at 94 °C for 4 min. After the second, which lasted 1 min, the hybridization process was started at a temperature of 55 °C for 1 min. This phase was followed by the elongation phase, carried out for 1 min at 72 °C. This is followed by another phase of elongation, done for 10 min at the same temperature as before. Those three phases (denaturation, hybridization and elongation) were carried out in 35 cycles. The PCR products were electrophoresed on 1.2 % agarose gel for 2 hours. Then, the gel was visualized using a transilluminator and then photographed.

Meristem culture conditions

The cultures were placed on shelves in the culture room according to a completely randomized device and incubated under a photoperiodic cycle of 12/12 hours and a temperature of 24 ± 2 °C. The light is provided by fluorescent lamps with an intensity of 3000 lux, at a relative humidity of 60 %.

Data analysis

The data collected during heat therapy of the ten cultivars, the number of rooted seedlings and the number of seedlings sanitized after thermotherapy coupled with the meristem culture were calculated with Excel 2010 software. The percentages of budburst and rooting were transformed by the Arcsinus \sqrt{x} angular formula and analyzed using the STATISTICA version 7.1 software. The analysis of variance has a factor (ANOVA 1) was used to compare the averages. When a significant difference is observed, the Newman-Keuls test is used to separate the means at the threshold $\alpha = 5 \%$.

RESULTS

Thermotherapy of cuttings

In this experiment, cuttings of different cultivars with symptoms of cassava mosaic disease were heat treated. After four weeks of incubation, the severity index of cassava mosaic disease was estimated and compare to severity before heat therapy. The results obtained are shown in Table 3. The analysis of this table shows that the average severity index of the disease was reduced following the treatment of thermotherapy. It ranged from 0.73 to 2.56 as opposed to a variation of 1.27 to 3.4 before thermotherapy. In addition, the highest disease severity index before (3.40) and after (2.50) thermotherapy was recorded in the cultivar Yacé.

The recovery rate in healthy plants after indexing by the TAS-ELISA test was calculated. The results obtained are shown in Table 4. The analysis of this table shows that the rate varied from 6.66 to 33.33 %. The highest rates of healthy plants recovery were recorded with the following cultivars: Afery, Diarassouba, Nsakperne, Antenne, Demoiselle, Six-mois and Zogloblé. On the other hand, cultivars with low rates of recovery of healthy plants are: Gnonrongouin (13.33 %), Glagban (13.33) and Yacé (6.66 %). The appearance of the leaves of two cultivars (Six-mois and Yacé) after thermotherapy is shown in Figure 3. The leaves of six-mois after heat treatment are colored uniform (green) and well full-blown without deformation (Figure 3a). In Yacé cuttings non-sanitized after heat treatment, the leaf blade has deformities and a mosaic color shown by red arrows (Figure 3b).

Association of thermotherapy with meristem culture

Effect of culture medium composition on shoot buds induction

Four (04) organogenesis media supplemented with different concentrations of growth hormones were used. Meristems excised from cuttings with leaves exhibiting cassava mosaic symptoms after thermotherapy treatment were placed on culture media. Four weeks later, experimental results were recorded in Table 5. Composition of the culture medium significantly influenced the rate of shoot buds induction from meristem

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explants with frequencies varying between 0 and 63.25 %. M2 and M3 media favored the emergence of shoot buds. The highest percentage (63.25 %) was recorded on M2 medium whereas no shoot induction was recorded on the control medium (Cm) and the M1 medium (1/2 MS + 0.5 mg/l BAP + 0.1 mg/l 2,4-D).

Effect of culture medium composition on the rooting of shoot buds

The leafy shoots were transferred on different rooting media. After four weeks of culture, the percentage of rooting was estimated. The results were recorded in Table 6. All the shoot buds (100 %) have rooted on the MS basal medium devoid of phytohormone. MS medium supplemented with BAP (0.05 mg / l) + NAA (0.01 mg / l) expressed a rooting frequency of 85.60 %.

Health status of the regenerated in vitro plants by PCR

Of a total of 26 samples, 22 were remediated, representing a remediation rate of 92.31 % (table 7). The Figure 4 illustrates two profiles of electrophoresis migration of PCR products. Figure 4a shows the migration pattern of virus free samples of cassava mosaic disease, while Figure 4b shows the migration profile of virus free samples and an un-sanitized sample (20A).

DISCUSSION

Cassava mosaic virus was removed from cassava cuttings treated with thermotherapy with a rate varying between 6 and 33 %. This difference in sanitation rates could be explained by a cultivar effect. Some cultivars are more susceptible to cassava mosaic disease than others. This is the case of the cultivar yacé whose sanitation rate is 6 %. Concerning viral particles neutralization in plant material could be explained by the temperature variation of 36 °C in the dark and 39 °C in the light (Sastry *et al*, 2014). Their work revealed that temperature conditions above 30 °C slow or block the replication of viruses. In addition, heat is important to the slowing or stopping of the multiplication of viral particles (Astier *et al*, 2001). The heat hinders the activity of the replicase and creates an instability of the viral particles. Moreover, in a condition of increase temperature, there is a weakening of the links between the protein subunits of the genetic material of the viruses. This induces cracks that cause their destruction by nucleases (Allam, 2000). The whole process of the viral cycle including replication and distribution that would be affected by the rise in temperature in this virus-plant interaction (Del Toro *et al*, 2015).

This methodology is based on the principle that the apical meristem does not contain or has very few viruses (Morel, 1948). In our study, the thermotherapy preceding the meristem culture would extend the apical zone devoid of viral particles around the meristem. Indeed, the alternation of the temperature (32 °C and 39 °C), would limit the movements of the viral particles towards the apical tissues. This facilitates the excision of a large meristem to generate plantlets. This would explain the high percentage of remediation (92.31%). Elimination of ACMV at 95 % by applying thermotherapy associated with meristem culture on four cassava accessions have been reported (Yandian, 2015). Sanitizing of potato infected with potato virus X (*Solanum tuberosum*) by combining thermotherapy and meristem culture have been successfully done (Li *et al*, 1994). Concerning sweet potato (*Ipomoea batatas*), similar results have been reported (Mervat, 2009). The results of their work showed the effectiveness of thermotherapy coupled with the meristem culture for the elimination of the marbling virus from sweet potato.

CONCLUSION

Cassava mosaic disease caused by the ACMV is a real threat to a sustainable cassava crop. The thermotherapy technique resulted in a recovery rate of 6 to 33 %, with the cultivar Yacé having the lowest rate of recovery of healthy plants is 6 %. The thermotherapy associated with meristem culture in this cultivar was able to neutralize the viral particles of cassava mosaic with a recovery rate of healthy plants of 92 %. The healthy in vitro plants will be acclimatized after a mass production from nodal segments and deliver to producers for field establishment.

REFERENCES

- i. Allam E.K. (2000). Eradication of Banana bunchy top virus and Banana mosaic virus, from diseased banana plants. *Annals of Agriculture Science.*, 45:33-48.

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- ii. Astier S., Albouy J., Maury Y. and Lecoq H. (2001). *Lutte contre les maladies à virus des plantes : le génie génétique pour la résistance*. In : *Principes de Virologie Végétale : Génome, Pouvoir Pathogène, Ecologie des Virus*. INRA (ed), France, p. 299-322.
- iii. Clark M.F. and Adams A.N. (1977). *Characteristics of the Microplate Method of ELISA for the detection of Plant viruses*. *Journal of General Virology.*, 34:475-483.
- iv. Del Toro F.J., Aguilar E., Hernández-Walias F.J., Tenllado F., Chung B.N. and Canto T. (2015). *High temperature, high ambient CO2 affect the interactions between three positive sense RNA viruses and a compatible host differentially, but not their silencing suppression efficiencies*. *PLoS One*,10: e0136062.
- v. Doyle J.J. and Doyle J.L. (1987). *A rapid DNA isolation procedure for small quantities of fresh leaf tissue*. *Phytochemical Bulletin.*, 19: 11-15.
- vi. FAO (2013). *Guide pour une intensification durable de la production*, Rome.
- vii. Hillocks R.J. and Jennings D.L. (2003). *Cassava brown streak disease a review of present knowledge and research needs*. *International Journal of Pest Management.*, 49: 225-234.
- viii. IITA (2000). *Annual report*.54p.
- ix. Jeremiah S.C., Ndyabula I.L., Mkamilo G.S., Haji S., Muhanna M.M., Chuwa C., Kasele S., Bouwmeester H., Ijumba J.N. and Legg J.P. (2015). *The dynamics and environmental influence on interactions between cassava brown streak disease et the whitefly, Bemisia tabaci*,*Phytopathology.*, 105(5):646-55.
- x. Legg J.P., Jeremiah S.C., Obiero H.M., Maruthi M.N., Ndyetabula I. and Okao-Okuja G. (2011). *Comparing the regional epidemiology of the cassava mosaic and cassava brown streak virus pandemics in Africa*. *Virus Research.*,159: 161-170.
- xi. Legg J.P. and Thresh J.M. (2003). *Cassava virus diseases in Africa. Proceedings of the first international conference on plant virology in Sub-Saharan Africa*. IITA, Ibadan, Nigeria, p. 517-552.
- xii. Li Y.H., He Y.K., Zhang Z.K., Lu H.F., Wu C.J. and Zheng P. (1994). *Study on virus-free potato seedlings from apical meristem culture in vitro*, *Xinan Nongye Xuebao*. *Southwest China Journal of Agricultural Sciences.*, 2: 28-31.
- xiii. Mervat M.M., Far E.L. and Ashoud A. (2009). *Utility of thermotherapy and meristem tip culture for freeing Sweet potato from viral infection*. *Australian Journal of Basic and Applied Sciences.*, 3 (1) :153-159.
- xiv. Morel G. (1948). *Recherches sur la culture associée de parasites obligatoires et de tissus végétaux*, *Annales des Epiphyties*, 1 : 123-234.
- xv. Munga T. and Thresh J.M. (2002). *Incidence of cassava mosaic and cassava brown streak virus diseases in coastal Kenya*. *Roots.*, 8 (1): 12-4.
- xvi. Murashige T. and Skoog F. (1962). *A revised medium for rapid growth and bio-assays with tobacco tissue cultures*. *Physiologia Plantarum.*, 15: 473 – 497.
- xvii. Mwamachi D.M., Muli B.M., Ndungu J.M., Muinga R.W. and Kiura J. (2005). *Research priorities for KARI-Mtwapa mandate area, coastal lowland (Kenya)*.
- xviii. N'zué B (2007). *Caractérisation morphologique, sélection variétale et amélioration du taux de multiplication végétative chez le manioc (Manihot esculenta Crantz (Euphorbiaceae))*. Thèse de doctorat, Université de Cocody, Abidjan. 141 p.
- xix. Ogwok E., Alicai T., Rey M., Beyen G. and Taylor N. (2015). *Distribution and accumulation of cassava brown streak viruses within infected cassava (Manihot esculenta Crantz) plants*. *Plant Pathology.*, 64 (5) :1235-1246.
- xx. Sastry K.S. and Zitter T.A. (2014). *Plant virus and viroid diseases in the tropics*, Springer Science + Business Media B.V. 2: 489p. doi: 10.1007/978-94-007-7820-7_2.
- xxi. Segnou (2002). *Développement végétatif et potentiel de rendement chez le manioc*. *Tropicultura.*, 20(4): 161-164.
- xxii. Thresh J.M. (2006). *Control of tropical plant virus diseases*. *Advance Virus Research.*, 67:245-295.
- xxiii. Toualy M.N.Y., Akinbade S.A., Séka K., Diallo H.A. and Kumar P.L. (2014). *Incidence and distribution of cassava mosaic begomoviruses in Côte d'Ivoire*. *International Journal of Agronomy and Agricultural Research.*, 4(6): 131-139.

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- xxiv. Wasswa P., Alicai T. and Mukasa S.B. (2010). Optimization of in vitro techniques for cassava brown streak virus elimination from infected cassava clones. *African Crop Science Journal.*, (4): 235 – 241.
- xxv. Yandian S.P., Gandonou B.C., Silla S., Zinga I., Dambier D. and Toukourou F. (2015). Elimination of african cassava mosaic virus (ACMV) in cassava (*Manihot esculenta* Crantz) using meristem culture associated to thermotherapy. *International Journal of Development Research.*, 05(10): 5655-5660.
- xxvi. Zapata C., Miller J.C. and Smith R.H. (1995). An in vitro procedure to eradicate Potato viruses X, Y and S from russet norkotah and two of its strains. *In vitro Cell Development Biology.*,31:153-159.

FIGURES LIST

Figure 1. Experimental device adopted for the thermotherapy of diseased cuttings of cassava mosaic

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Figure 2. Different steps of thermotherapy associated to meristem culture of cultivar Yacé. (a) emission of young buds. (b) twigs containing the meristematic buds. (c) meristem sampling. (d) meristems on culture medium. (e) leafy shoot from meristem after three weeks of culture. (f) evolution of the leafy shoot into seedling.

Figure 3. Leaves of cassava plants after a treatment of thermotherapy. (a) Cultivar six-mois sanitized with healthy leaves; (b) non-sanitized Yacé cultivar, the red arrows indicate cassava mosaic disease symptoms.

Figure 4. Electrophoresis of PCR products of cassava leaf samples after thermotherapy associated with meristem culture. (a) gel showing seven virus free samples. (b) gel contract seven samples with CVMA-positive Sample 20. M = molecular weight marker. 1Kb= DNA Ladder size. A = ACMV. E = EACMV. TA +(ACMV positive control = 783 bp). TE + (positive indicator EACMV = 780 bp). TA- (ACMV negative light). TE- (Negative Witness EACMV).

TABLES LIST

Table 1. Composition of culture media

Media	Basal media	BAP	ANA	GA ₃	2,4-D
Control media (Cm)	MS + Vit MS	-	-	-	-
Medium 1 (M1)	1/2 MS + Vit MS	0.5 mg/L	-	-	0.1m g/L
Medium 2 (M2)	MS + Vit MS	0.1 mg/l	0.2 mg/l	0.04 mg/l	-
Medium 3 (M3)	MS + Vit MS	0.15 mg/l	0.18 mg/l	0.02 mg/l	-

MS : Murashige and Skoog, Vit MS : MS Vitamins

Table 2. PCR reagents for the preparation of master mix

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Reagents	Initial concentration	Volume	Final concentration
Tampon green colorless	5 X	5µl	1 X
MgCl ₂	25 mM	1 µl	1 mM
dNTP	10 mM	0,5 µl	0,2 mM
Primer JSP001	10 µM	1 µl	0,4 µM
Primer JSP002 (ACMV) or JSP003 (EACMV)	10 µM	1 µl	0,4 µM
GoTaq [®] Polymerase	5 u/µl	0,125 µl	0,625 u
Distilled water	-	11,375 µl	-

(JSP001) F 5'-ATGTCGAAGCGACCAGGAGAT-3'	(JSP001) F 5'-ATGTCGAAGCGACCAGGAGAT-3'
(JSP002) R 5'-TGTTTATTAATTGCCAATACT-3'	(JSP003) R 5'-CCTTTATTAATTTGTCACCTGC-3'
Primer sequence against ACMV Protein Shell	Primer sequence against EACMV Protein Shell

Table 3. Effect of heat therapy on the disease severity index in ten cultivars showing symptoms of cassava mosaic disease

Cultivars	Average severity index before heat therapy	Average severity index after thermotherapy
Gnonrongouin	2,27±0,11b	1,60±0,21b
Glagban	2,80±0,35ab	1,73±0,27b
Zogloble	2,73±0,31ab	1,40±0,16b
Yacé	3,40±0,21a	2,56±0,28a
Antenne	2,73±0,11ab	1,80±0,24b
Nsakperne	1,93±0,34b	1,47±0,16b
Demoiselle	2,87±0,16ab	1,73±0,11b
Afery	2,58±0,12a	1,60±0,21b
Diarassouba	2,58±0,12a	1,60±0,13b
Six mois	1,27±0,22c	0,73±0,11c
F	6,39	8,25
P	< 0,000	< 0,000

The figures followed by the same letter are statistically identical to the threshold $\alpha = 5\%$ (Newman-keuls test); Mean \pm standard error.

Table 4. Indexing and recovery rates of healthy plants after thermotherapy treatment

Cultivars	Serological status	Number of cuttings by serological status after thermotherapy	Recovery rate of healthy plants after thermotherapy (%)
<i>Gnonrongouin</i>	+	13	13,33
	-	02	
<i>Glagban</i>	+	13	13,33
	-	02	
<i>Zogloblé</i>	+	10	33,33
	-	05	
<i>Yacé</i>	+	14	06,66
	-	01	
<i>Antenne</i>	+	12	20,00
	-	03	
<i>Nsakperne</i>	+	11	20,00
	-	04	
<i>Demoiselle</i>	+	12	20,00
	-	03	
<i>Afery</i>	+	05	33,33
	-	10	
<i>Diarassouba</i>	+	10	33,33
	-	05	
<i>Six-mois</i>	+	10	33,33
	-	05	

+: no virus-free sample. -: virus-free sample,

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Table 5. Shoot buds induction from meristem explants of cultivar Yacé after a treatment of thermotherapy

Culture media	Percentage of meristem explants inducing shoot buds (%)
Control medium(Cm)	0.00±0.00 c
Medium 1 (M1)	0.00±0.00 c
Medium 2 (M2)	63.25±9.00 a
Medium 3 (M3)	11.75±7.43 b
Statistics	$\frac{P}{F}$
	$\frac{<0.000}{26.720}$

In the same column, the mean \pm standard deviation followed by the same letter are statistically identical at $\alpha = 5\%$ threshold (Newman-keuls test).

Table 6. Effect of the composition of the culture medium on the rooting of seedlings

Basal media	BAP (mg/l)	ANA(mg/l)	Percentage of rooting (%)
MS	0	0	100 a
MS	0.05	0.01	85.60 b

Table 7. Percentage of sanited after thermotherapy combined with Yacé cultivar meristem culture

Number of treated plantlets	Number of sick seedlings	Number of viruses-free plantlets	Percentage of recovery of healthy plantlets (%)
26	04	22	92,31